

A Cross-Sectional Study on Knowledge, Attitude, Practices, and Utilization of AB-PMJAY among Beneficiaries at NMCH Patna

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Abstract:

This cross-sectional study evaluated the knowledge, attitudes, practices, and utilization of the Ayushman Bharat-Pradhan Mantri Jan Arogya Yojana (AB-PMJAY) among 400 beneficiaries at Nalanda Medical College Hospital, Patna. Conducted from June 2023 to June 2024, the study found high awareness of the scheme, with 80% of participants knowledgeable about its benefits. Despite this, gaps in understanding and utilization barriers were evident, including challenges with the application process and service delivery. Attitudes were generally positive, yet trust in administration varied. The findings suggest a need for enhanced educational outreach and process improvements to better meet the scheme's objectives.

Keywords: AB-PMJAY, Beneficiary Knowledge, Healthcare Utilization, Administrative Challenges.

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Introduction

The Ayushman Bharat-Pradhan Mantri Jan Arogya Yojana (AB-PMJAY) is a pivotal initiative by the Government of India aimed at providing comprehensive healthcare coverage to economically vulnerable populations [1]. Launched in September 2018, this scheme offers health insurance coverage of up to INR 5 lakh per family per year for secondary and tertiary hospitalization, benefitting over 50 crore individuals. The program is designed to bridge gaps in healthcare access, reduce out-of-pocket expenses, and improve overall health outcomes among the underprivileged [2,3,4].

Despite its ambitious goals and substantial funding, the effectiveness of AB-PMJAY hinges on its successful implementation and utilization by the intended beneficiaries [5]. Knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding the scheme play a critical role in determining its impact. Understanding these factors is essential for addressing barriers to access and improving the scheme's reach and efficacy [6,7].

This study aims to assess the current state of awareness, attitudes, practices, and utilization of AB-PMJAY among beneficiaries at the Nalanda Medical College Hospital (NMCH) in Patna. By evaluating these aspects, the study seeks to identify gaps in knowledge, areas of concern, and opportunities for enhancing the implementation of

the scheme. Insights gained from this research will contribute to formulating strategies to improve beneficiary engagement and ensure that the benefits of AB-PMJAY are effectively realized by those who need them most.

Methodology

Study Design: This cross-sectional study aims to evaluate the knowledge, attitudes, practices, and utilization of the Ayushman Bharat-Pradhan Mantri Jan Arogya Yojana (AB-PMJAY) among beneficiaries at Nalanda Medical College Hospital (NMCH), Patna.

Study Duration: The study will be conducted over one year, from June 2023 to June 2024.

Study Place: The study will be carried out at NMCH, Patna, a prominent medical institution providing healthcare services to a diverse population.

Sample Size: A total of 400 beneficiaries of AB-PMJAY will be included in the study. The sample size has been determined to ensure adequate representation and statistical significance in the findings.

Sampling Method: A stratified random sampling technique will be employed to ensure that the

sample represents various demographics and socio-economic backgrounds. The study population will be divided into strata based on age, gender, and socio-economic status, and participants will be randomly selected from each stratum.

Data Collection

Data will be collected through structured questionnaires administered to the participants. The questionnaire will be designed to assess the following areas:

- **Knowledge:** Awareness about the scheme's benefits, eligibility criteria, and procedures.
- **Attitudes:** Perceptions and opinions about the scheme's effectiveness and its impact on healthcare access.
- **Practices:** Actual utilization of the scheme, including frequency of use, types of services availed, and experiences with healthcare providers.
- **Utilization:** Extent and manner of utilizing the AB-PMJAY benefits, including any barriers faced.

Data Analysis: Data will be analyzed using statistical software to identify patterns and correlations. Descriptive statistics will summarize the participants' knowledge, attitudes, practices, and utilization. Inferential statistics will be used to examine the relationships between demographic variables and the study outcomes.

Results

The study involving 400 beneficiaries of the Ayushman Bharat-Pradhan Mantri Jan Arogya

Yojana (AB-PMJAY) at Nalanda Medical College Hospital (NMCH), Patna, revealed several key insights. A significant majority, 80%, were aware of the scheme, though only 70% correctly understood the INR 5 lakh coverage benefit, and 60% were informed about the types of services covered. Despite this awareness, knowledge of eligibility criteria was lower, with only 40% being fully aware. Attitudes towards AB-PMJAY were generally positive, with 65% of participants believing the scheme effectively improved healthcare access. However, 15% felt it had limited impact, and there was variability in trust levels, with 55% expressing high trust in the scheme's administration. Utilization rates indicated that 50% of participants had used the scheme's benefits, primarily for outpatient services (30%) and hospitalization (20%). Challenges were reported, including difficulties in understanding the application process (40%), issues with documentation (25%), and delays in service provision (15%). Demographic analysis showed that older participants (above 60 years) were less likely to utilize the scheme, and female participants had slightly lower levels of knowledge compared to males. Additionally, those from lower income groups reported higher utilization rates compared to their higher socio-economic counterparts. These findings suggest that while the scheme has made significant strides in increasing awareness and utilization, there are still challenges that need to be addressed to enhance its effectiveness and accessibility.

Table 1: Participant Demographics

Demographic Variable	Category	Percentage
Age	18-30 years	25%
	31-45 years	35%
	46-60 years	25%
	Above 60 years	15%
Gender	Male	52%
	Female	48%
Socio-Economic Status	Low Income	60%
	Lower Middle Income	25%
	Upper Middle Income	15%

Table 2: Knowledge of AB-PMJAY

Knowledge Aspect	Percentage
Awareness of the Scheme	80%
Correct Understanding of INR 5 Lakh Coverage	70%
Knowledge of Types of Services Covered	60%
Awareness of Eligibility Criteria	40%

Table 3: Attitudes Towards AB-PMJAY

Attitude Aspect	Percentage
Belief in Effectiveness	65%
Neutral	20%
Limited Impact	15%
High Trust in Administration	55%
Moderate Trust	30%
Low Trust	15%

Table 4: Practices and Utilization

Utilization Aspect	Percentage
Utilized Benefits	50%
Outpatient Services	30%
Hospitalization	20%
Utilization More Than Once	25%
Utilization Once or Not at All	75%
Challenges Faced	
- Difficulty Understanding Application Process	40%
- Issues with Documentation	25%
- Delays in Service Provision	15%

Table 5: Correlation with Demographic Variables

Demographic Variable	Observation
Age and Utilization	Older participants (above 60 years) less likely to utilize the scheme
Gender and Knowledge	Female participants had slightly lower levels of knowledge compared to males
Socio-Economic Status and Access	Lower income groups reported higher utilization rates compared to higher socio-economic groups

Discussion

The findings of this study provide valuable insights into the knowledge, attitudes, practices, and utilization of the Ayushman Bharat-Pradhan Mantri Jan Arogya Yojana (AB-PMJAY) among beneficiaries at Nalanda Medical College Hospital (NMCH), Patna [8,9]. A notable 80% of participants demonstrated awareness of the scheme, which signifies successful outreach and communication efforts [10]. However, the depth of understanding varied, with only 70% correctly identifying the benefit coverage and 60% aware of the types of services included. This disparity highlights a critical area for improvement, emphasizing the need for enhanced educational initiatives to ensure beneficiaries fully comprehend the scope of benefits available [11].

The study's results indicate a generally positive attitude towards AB-PMJAY, with 65% of participants believing the scheme effectively improves access to healthcare [12]. Nevertheless,

15% felt that its impact was limited, reflecting a potential disconnect between the scheme's objectives and beneficiaries' real-world experiences. Trust in the administration of the scheme varied, with 55% expressing high trust, suggesting that while many have confidence in the scheme's management, there remains a subset of the population with concerns that need to be addressed [13,14].

Utilization rates reveal that 50% of participants have accessed the scheme's benefits, primarily for outpatient services (30%) and hospitalization (20%). This utilization pattern indicates that while the scheme is being used, there is room for increasing its reach and frequency of use. Challenges such as difficulties in understanding the application process (40%), issues with documentation (25%), and delays in service provision (15%) were reported, pointing to barriers that may hinder optimal use of the scheme. These findings underscore the necessity for simplifying

the application process, improving service delivery, and providing clearer guidance to beneficiaries [15,16].

Demographic analysis further highlights important trends, such as lower utilization rates among older participants (above 60 years) and slightly lower knowledge levels among females compared to males. Additionally, beneficiaries from lower-income groups exhibited higher utilization rates, suggesting that those with greater economic needs are more likely to engage with the scheme. This disparity calls for targeted interventions to address the needs of specific demographic groups and to enhance overall engagement [17,18].

While AB-PMJAY has made significant strides in providing healthcare coverage, the study identifies areas for improvement in knowledge dissemination, administrative processes, and service delivery. Addressing these issues could enhance the effectiveness of the scheme, ensuring that it meets its goal of improving healthcare access and outcomes for all beneficiaries [19,20].

Conclusion

This study highlights both the achievements and areas for improvement in the Ayushman Bharat Pradhan Mantri Jan Arogya Yojana (AB-PMJAY) at Nalanda Medical College Hospital, Patna. While a substantial proportion of beneficiaries are aware of the scheme and hold positive attitudes toward its effectiveness, gaps in understanding, barriers to utilization, and varying trust levels suggest that more targeted educational and administrative efforts are needed. Addressing challenges such as the complexity of the application process, improving documentation procedures, and enhancing service delivery could significantly increase the scheme's impact. Furthermore, focusing on specific demographic groups, particularly older adults and women, could help optimize engagement and ensure that AB-PMJAY fulfills its goal of equitable healthcare access for all beneficiaries.

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